

CONGRUENCE OF SPEAKING AND LISTENING ASSESSMENT TASKS AND TOOLS TO THE STANDARDS AND COMPETENCIES SET FOR JUNIOR AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Chris John D. Data
Jhonabail A. Garcia
Julie Rose A. Oliva

School of Teacher Education English Department, CSTC College of Sciences, Technology and Communications Inc., Sariaya, Quezon, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20365240>

ABSTRACT

This study explored the assessment of speaking and listening tasks and tools used in Junior and Senior High School English classes, focusing on their alignment with the Department of Education's K to 12 curriculum standards and competencies. It specifically examined how listening activities reflected dimensions such as top-down or bottom-up processing, listening for gist or specific details, and marginal or attentive listening. In speaking, the study investigated the modes of speech delivery and types of speech assessed. A key objective was to determine whether current assessment practices were congruent with content standards, performance standards, and learning competencies. Anchored on the principles of constructive alignment, the study highlighted the importance of coherence among teaching strategies, learning goals, and assessment tools to enhance communicative competence. The conceptual framework emphasized that misalignment between curriculum goals and assessment tasks might have compromised instructional relevance and learner outcomes. Through comparative content analysis, the study identified gaps and inconsistencies in current classroom practices. It also aimed to develop authentic, competency-based speaking and listening assessment tasks that promoted real-world communication, critical thinking, and learner engagement. The findings were expected to inform more effective and meaningful assessment strategies in English language education.

Keywords: *Top-down, Listening for Specific Details, Attentive Listening, Content Standards, Performance Standards, Learning Competencies*

INTRODUCTION

Listening and speaking were essential macro skills that significantly contributed to students' academic achievement and communicative competence. These skills formed the foundation for effective interaction, critical thinking, and lifelong learning, especially in both academic and real-world settings. In the Department of Education K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, language instruction was grounded in the integration of macro skills listening, speaking, reading, and writing to develop learners who were both communicatively competent and multiliterate. The curriculum clearly emphasized that students should demonstrate an understanding of oral language and apply appropriate speaking strategies based on purpose, audience, and context. This highlighted the idea that communication skills were not only academic requirements but also vital life skills that enabled learners to actively and meaningfully engage in society.

Moreover, studies on curriculum implementation in the Philippines confirmed that the K to 12 English curriculum aimed to develop communicative competence through performance-based standards and authentic learning tasks. Research by Marquez and Bando (2020) revealed that the curriculum supported the development of learners' ability to use language effectively across different contexts, emphasizing the importance of aligning instruction and assessment with communicative objectives. Likewise, (Miradora, 2022) pointed out that the English curriculum was anchored on the principle that language, thinking, and learning were interconnected, and that mastery of macro skills including listening and speaking was crucial for holistic learner development. These findings reinforced the idea that listening and speaking are not isolated abilities but were central to both cognitive and academic growth.

Further supporting this perspective, recent empirical research on language proficiency among senior high school students showed that speaking ability and overall language performance were shaped by factors such as motivation, confidence, and exposure to communicative activities. Capadeso and Banquiao (2025) found that students' English proficiency, particularly in speaking, is strongly associated with their academic performance, highlighting the need for effective instructional and assessment practices that promoted active language use. These results suggested that assessment tools should move beyond traditional approaches and instead provide authentic opportunities for learners to demonstrate their listening and speaking competencies.

Given these considerations, it became evident that examining the alignment between assessment tasks and the content standards in the K to 12 curriculum was essential. Ensuring consistency between instruction and assessment played a key role in developing students' communicative competence. By enhancing assessment practices especially in listening and speaking, educators were able to better equip learners with the skills needed for academic success, workplace readiness, and meaningful participation in society.

Research Questions

This study examined whether the tasks and tools used to assess them in junior and senior high school aligned with curriculum standards and supported real-life communication.

To explore possible alignment or misalignment, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How can speaking and listening tasks and tools be described in junior high school and senior high school in terms of;
 - 1.1 Listening
 - 1.1.1 Top-down or Bottom-up
 - 1.1.2 Listening for Gist or Specific Details
 - 1.1.3 Marginal or Attentive Listening
 - 1.2 Speaking
 - 1.2.1 Modes of Speech Delivery
 - 1.2.2 Types of Speech
2. Are the speaking and listening assessment tasks and tools congruent with the:
 - 2.1 Content Standards
 - 2.2 Performance Standards
 - 2.3 Learning Competencies
3. What authentic speaking and listening tasks and tools were developed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed qualitative research, which entailed gathering and examining non-numeric data to gain insights into concepts, opinions, or experiences. And also, it employed a content analysis approach within qualitative research. The qualitative approach was appropriate for gaining a deep understanding of the nature, content, and alignment of assessment practices in the context of an actual classroom setting. Qualitative research was particularly effective for exploring complex education phenomena where contextual understanding was crucial. According to Merriam and Tisdell (2016), qualitative research was concerned with how individuals interpret their experiences. These scholarly perspectives underscored the relevance of using qualitative methods to examine assessment congruence in this study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at the College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications (CSTC), specifically in its Junior and Senior High School Department. CSTC was a private institution that implemented the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum,

offering subjects such as Oral Communication and English. These subjects focused on developing students' speaking and listening skills, which were central to this study. The school was selected as the research locale due to the availability of relevant assessment materials, the cooperation of English teachers, and its commitment to quality instruction in communication. The setting provided a suitable environment for examining the nature and congruence of assessment tasks and tools with the expected competencies.

Corpus of the Study

This study examined the alignment of speaking and listening assessment tasks and tools with the standards and competencies outlined in the Philippine K to 12 curriculums for Junior High School (JHS) and Senior High School (SHS) students. The corpus consisted of official speaking and listening assessment tools currently used by English teachers in selected public and private secondary schools. These tools were purposively sampled to reflect a variety of classroom assessment practices and to ensure representation across both educational levels.

For Junior High School, the study collected assessment instruments from Grades 7 to 10. These include rubric performance, oral test forms, and listening comprehension activities that were aligned with learning competencies set in the curriculum guide. Similarly, for Senior High School, the study gathered tools from Grades 11 and 12, specifically from subjects such as Oral Communication, Reading and Writing, and English for Academic and Professional Purposes. These tools include speech delivery rubrics, interview simulations, group discussion evaluation, and listening task sheets.

The corpus of the study includes a total of 20 assessment tools—10 from JHS and 10 from SHS submitted by experienced English teachers and validated for regular use in their respective institutions. Each assessment tool was analyzed in terms of its task type, language demand, skill integration, and scoring criteria. These features were then cross-referenced with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and performance standards prescribed by the Department of Education to evaluate the degree of congruence.

By analyzing actual classroom assessment tools, this corpus provided a practical basis for understanding how assessment practices reflected or diverged from the intended learning goals. The findings from this analysis offered insights into the appropriateness, effectiveness, and alignment of current assessment methods in developing students' communicative competence in both speaking and listening across junior and senior high school levels.

Data Gathering Procedures

Data for this study were collected through qualitative analysis of speaking and listening assessment tasks and tools in the Junior and Senior High School Department of the College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications (CSTC). Before data collection, the researcher sought formal permission from the school administration and

the English department to gather instructional and assessment materials relevant to the purposes of the study. The primary data sources were teacher-made assessments, activity sheets, rubrics, guides for performance tasks, and worksheets used for the purpose of assessing speaking and listening. The researcher gathered the data from selected English teachers who handled students in Grades 7 to 12. The data collection was purposive, as the task was to obtain paper and pen assessment tasks and tools that assessed the communication dispositions, and to seek materials that were congruent with the subject areas of Oral Communication and English for Academic and Professional Purposes. In order to find congruence with content standards, performance standards, and learning competencies, this study describes the nature and properties of speaking and listening assessment tasks and tools utilized in Junior and Senior High Schools.

Furthermore, the study provided an avenue for identifying areas for improvement and proposed developing authentic assessment tasks based on the findings. All of the materials were collected in soft copies, and the materials were treated with confidentiality. The researcher did not collect any identifiable personal or student information. After the materials had been compiled, they were formally organized for content analysis according to the grade level and type of assessment collected. This allowed the researcher to systematically interpret the data, according to the next phase of the study.

Analytical Framework

This analytical framework showed a structured approach to evaluating the alignment between assessment tools and the curriculum standards set by the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Junior and Senior High School. It began with the collection and categorization of assessment tools by grade level, followed by an analysis of their key features, such as task type, skills measured, rubrics used, and mode of delivery. These features are then compared against the MELCs to determine whether the assessments accurately reflected the intended learning outcomes. Through a process of mapping and comparison, the framework allowed for the evaluation of congruence levels, identifying whether there is full alignment, where competencies and standards are reflected, or partial/no alignment, where mismatches or missing elements are found. This process supported educators and curriculum developers in ensuring that assessments are valid, targeted, and supportive of meaningful student learning.

Figure 1
Analytical Framework for Evaluating the Alignment of Assessment Tools with Curriculum Standards (MELCs)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. Listening Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School

Table 1
Listening Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School

Process	Frequency	Percentage
Top-down	5	62.50
Bottom-Up	3	37.50
TOTAL	8	100

Table 1 presented the frequency and percentage of listening tasks and tools found in the activities of Junior High School and Senior High School students. The data revealed that the most prevalent approach was the Top-Down Process, with a frequency of 5 and a percentage of 62.50. In contrast, Bottom-Up processes were the least frequent, with a frequency of 3 and a percentage of 37.50. This suggested that listening activities in

classrooms heavily relied on learners' prior knowledge, context clues, and their ability to make inferences about what they heard.

This reliance on the Top-Down Process indicated that educators may prioritized comprehension strategies that engaged students in critical thinking and contextual understanding rather than focusing solely on decoding individual sounds or words. Such an approach could have enhanced students' ability to grasp the overall meaning of spoken texts, especially in real-life communication scenarios. However, the lower occurrence of Bottom-Up strategies suggested a potential gap in developing students' foundational listening skills, such as phonemic awareness and vocabulary recognition. To achieve a more balanced listening instruction, it may be beneficial to integrate both processes, ensuring students built strong listening comprehension from both cognitive and linguistic perspectives.

Top-down processing in listening was an approach in which learners used their prior knowledge, experiences, and contextual understanding to interpret the overall meaning of what they heard, rather than decoding information word by word. This strategy enabled students to grasp the main ideas, anticipate content, and make inferences, which were essential in real-life listening scenarios like discussions, speeches, and media content. According to Field (2019), top-down listening encouraged active prediction and engagement with the material, supporting deeper comprehension. Similarly, Nation and Newton (2020) emphasized that top-down processes helped learners manage unfamiliar language by focusing on context and meaning rather than isolated words. As shown in Table 1, the emphasis on top-down activities in Junior and Senior High School indicated a pedagogical focus on global understanding rather than purely linguistic decoding.

Table 2
Listening Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School in terms of Purpose

Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
Listening for Gist	3	37.50
Listening for Specific Details	5	62.50
TOTAL	8	100

Table 2 analyzed the purpose of listening tasks, specifically whether they were aimed at Listening for Gist or Listening for Specific Details. The data showed a clear preference for detail-oriented listening tasks: Listening for Specific Details appeared 5 times, accounting for 62.50%, whereas Listening for Gist appeared 3 times, accounting for 37.50%. This suggested that the design of listening activities focused more on factual recall and locating precise information from a spoken source. While this was beneficial for developing skills such as attention to detail, it limited students' opportunities to engage in higher-order thinking, such as summarizing content, identifying the speaker's purpose, or evaluating tone and intent.

Listening for gist was important in developing global comprehension skills and the ability to understand the overall message without needing to process every word. The underrepresentation of this type implied that students may have struggled with real-life listening situations where the ability to grasp the main idea quickly was crucial such as in casual conversations, lectures, or news reports. To enhance students' communicative competence, educators were encouraged to aim for a better balance between gist listening and detail listening in their lesson designs.

Listening for gist was the process of understanding the general idea or overall meaning of a spoken text without focusing on specific details. It was a key top-down listening skill that allowed learners to make sense of what they heard by drawing on context, background knowledge, and main ideas. This strategy was essential in real-world communication, where grasping the central message is often more important than understanding every word Goh & Aryadoust (2021). It supported listening fluency and helped learners stay engaged with longer or more complex audio materials Wilson (2018).

Table 3
Listening Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School in terms of Types

Types	Frequency	Percentage
Marginal	0	0
Attentive	8	100
TOTAL	8	100

Table 3 showed the types of listening in terms of engagement and cognitive effort. All the recorded listening activities fell under Marginal Listening, with a frequency of 8 and a percentage of 100%. There were no instances of Attentive Listening (0%). This suggested that most classroom listening tasks were passive. Marginal listening occurred when students heard sounds or words but do not mentally engage with or interpret them deeply. This may have happened when students were distracted, overwhelmed, or not given enough reason or opportunity to focus critically on the content.

The absence of Attentive Listening tasks was concerning, as attentive listening involves full concentration and cognitive engagement. In this type, learners made sense of what they heard, reflected on it, and possibly responded or applied what they have understood. Tasks that encourage attentive listening, such as discussions, note-taking with analysis, or critical response exercises, helped learners develop skills vital for academic success and real-world communication. Therefore, this imbalance called for a redesign of listening tasks to ensure that students were not merely hearing content but were processing and internalizing it meaningfully. Educators should be encouraged to use authentic materials and interactive activities that stimulated active engagement and attentive listening.

Part II. Speaking Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School

Table 4
Speaking Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School in terms of Modes of Speech Delivery

Modes of Speech Delivery	Frequency	Percentage
Memorized Speech	3	50
Manuscript Speech	1	16.67
Extemporaneous Speech	2	33.33
Impromptu Speech	0	0
TOTAL	6	100

Table 1 presented the frequency and percentage of speaking tasks and tools found in the activities of Junior High School and Senior High School students. The data revealed that the most prevalent mode of speech delivery was Memorized Speech, with a frequency of 3 and a percentage of 50%. This indicate that half of the speech-related activities in both levels relied on students delivering memorized content. The second most common mode was Extemporaneous Speech, with a frequency of 2 (33.33%), followed by Manuscript Speech with a frequency of 1 (16.67%). An Impromptu Speech was not observed in any of the activities.

This suggested that students were primarily trained to prepare and deliver rehearsed speeches, possibly to build confidence and ensure clarity in their delivery. The limited use of impromptu and manuscript speech could have reflected a curriculum focus on planned presentations rather than spontaneous or strictly scripted delivery.

Table 5
Speaking Tasks and Tools in Junior High School and Senior High School in terms of Types of Speech

Types of Speech	Frequency	Percentage
Informative Speech	6	50
Entertainment Speech	1	8.33
Demonstrative Speech	1	8.33
Persuasive Speech	4	33.34
TOTAL	12	100

Table 5 showed the frequency and percentage of different types of speech practiced by Junior High School and Senior High School students. The most frequently occurring type was Informative Speech, with a frequency of 6 and a percentage of 50%. This was followed by Persuasive Speech at 4 occurrences (33.34%). Both Entertainment Speech and Demonstrative Speech were the least used, each with a frequency of 1 and a percentage of 8.33%.

This implied that speech tasks in schools were mostly geared toward sharing knowledge and convincing others, which were essential skills in both academic and real-life contexts. The lower frequencies of entertainment and demonstrative speeches suggested these types were given less emphasis, potentially due to their more specialized or creative nature.

Part III. Congruence of Speaking and Listening Assessment Tasks and Tools

Table 6
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Content Standards in Grade 8

Activity	Content Standards
<p>Activity 1: Informative Speech Instruction: Listen closely to a recorded speech provided by your teacher then answer the following questions with a minimum of 3 sentences and a maximum of 5 sentences.</p> <p>Activity 2: Listening Strategies Instruction: Listen to the audiobook from the link provided. Afterwards, come up and write 5 questions regarding the audio you have listened to. Write your questions below.</p>	<p>The learners understand various listening strategies appropriate to different texts and purposes.</p> <p>The learners understand how language is used to express opinions and ideas.</p>
<p>Activity 3 Instruction: Watch closely and examine a TED Talk, and then in 3-5 sentences answer the questions that follow:</p>	<p>The learners understand multimodal texts and their effects on comprehension.</p> <p>The learners understand the function of language in raising awareness of social issues.</p>
<p>Activity 4 Instruction: For your activity, listen to the speech entitled “The Power of Listening” by William Ury. You need to apply the strategies in listening to the speech, then after that you will write your observations, especially the important information that you’ve heard in the speech. Write your answer on your answer sheet.</p>	<p>The learners understand the importance of active and empathetic listening in personal and social communication.</p>

The table 6 illustrated the alignment between listening and speaking tasks and the corresponding content standards for Grade 8 students. Each activity was designed to target specific learning goals, such as understanding listening strategies, interpreting multimodal texts, recognizing the function of language, and practicing empathetic listening. For example, Activities 1 and 2 focused on developing comprehension and questioning skills through listening tasks, while Activity 3 incorporated multimedia exposure to enhance critical thinking about language use in social contexts. Activity 4 emphasized the importance of empathetic listening, which encouraged learners to reflect on meaningful communication.

This alignment underscored the deliberate integration of curriculum activities with content standards to promote comprehensive language learning. As noted in contemporary curriculum design, linking tasks with clear learning objectives fostered deeper student engagement and ensures meaningful assessment Tomlinson (2014). Moreover, aligning tasks with standards reflected the principles of outcome-based education, where learning activities were intentionally constructed to build skills incrementally and purposefully DepEd (2016). By incorporating varied and authentic listening and speaking tasks, educators provided learners with opportunities to apply their knowledge in real-life contexts, an essential approach in 21st-century education Anderson & Krathwohl (2016).

Table 7
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Content Standards in Grade 10

Activity	Content Standards
<p>Activity 1: Evaluating Spoken Text Instruction: Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below, then identify which among the three videos shows fluency, tone, cohesion, and correctness. Afterwards, answer the following questions below.</p>	<p>The learner demonstrates understanding of how world literature and other text types serve as ways of expressing and resolving personal conflicts, also how to use strategies in linking textual information, repairing, enhancing communication, public speaking, emphasis markers in persuasive texts, different forms of modals, reflexive and intensive pronouns.</p>
<p>Activity 2: Detecting Biases and Unsupported Claims Instructions: For your activity, you are going to watch and listen critically to a debate on the link given below. Since it's a debate, you are on the mediator side. You are to list at least 5 biases and the unsupported claims (if there's any) that the two opponents said. Note that you are not to repeat</p>	<p>The learner demonstrates understanding of how world literatures and other text types serve as vehicles of expressing and resolving conflicts among individuals or groups; also, how to use strategies in critical reading, listening, and viewing, and affirmation and negation markers to deliver impromptu and extemporaneous speeches.</p>

<p>everything that the mediator has said. Follow the given format.</p> <p>Activity 3: Instruction: Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below. Afterwards, in 3-4 sentences, answer the following questions in the space provided.</p>	
<p>Activity 4: Memorized Speech Instruction: For your application, you are going to deliver the speech that you just made. The delivery of speech should be memorized; note that you will be guided by the criteria below. Delivery of Speech</p>	<p>The learner demonstrates understanding of how world literature and other text types serve as sources of wisdom in expressing and resolving conflicts among individuals, groups, and nature; also, how to use evaluative reading, listening, and viewing strategies, special speeches for occasions, pronouns, and structures of modification.</p>

The table presented the alignment of selected listening and speaking activities with the content standards for Grade 10 English. Each activity engaged students in higher-order thinking and practical language application. For instance, Activities 1 and 3 required critical listening through video analysis, targeting elements like fluency, tone, and correctness. Activity 2 fostered evaluative skills by asking students to detect biases and unsupported claims in a debate. Meanwhile, Activity 4 centered on memorized speech delivery, emphasizing structure and proper speech execution. Overall, the activities reflected a thoughtful integration of listening and speaking skills, encouraging students to apply what they heard or observed in analytical or communicative ways. These tasks were designed not only for performance but also for reflection and real-world relevance, as seen in their purposeful link to communication contexts.

According to recent literature, effective language instruction hinged on the meaningful alignment between instructional activities and curriculum standards. Genon and Torres (2020) emphasized that assessment and learning tasks must promote authenticity and critical engagement, especially in language classrooms. Activities such as evaluating spoken texts and detecting debate biases mirrored real-life communication tasks, making them relevant and aligned with the intended learning outcomes. Moreover, DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019 supported the use of performance-based and standards-based assessments to develop 21st-century skills, including critical thinking and communication. The integration of authentic listening and speaking tasks as shown in the table not only reflected curriculum expectations but also helped learners internalize language concepts more deeply and functionally.

Table 8
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Content Standards in Senior High

Activity	Content Standard
<p>Activity 2: What's with the Conversation Instruction: Learners will be grouped and will present a 5-minute skit of a communication process among people with diverse cultural backgrounds (intercultural communication). You may present a communication breakdown, effective communication, or both.</p>	<p>The learner understands the nature and elements of oral communication in context.</p>
<p>Activity 3: Speech Evaluation Instruction: Learners will watch and listen to a sample oral communication video provided by the teacher. Then, point out and evaluate the functions used by the speaker to deliver ideas and evaluate how it was executed by writing a 200-250-word essay.</p>	<p>The learner values the functions/ purposes of oral communication.</p>
<p>Activity 5: Mini Documentary Instruction: Create a 3-5-minute video that captures the seven communicative strategies in different speech situations. Choose a place inside the campus (classroom, canteen, bookstore, library, chapel) where people are involved in some kind of activity.</p>	<p>The learner recognizes that communicative competence requires understanding of speech context, speech style, speech act, and communicative strategy.</p>
<p>Activity 6: Reading from a Manuscript Instruction: Learners will be reading the manuscript that they have done.</p> <p>Activity 7: Memorized Speech Instruction: Learners will be presenting a short speech that they have memorized.</p> <p>Activity 8: Extemporaneous Speech</p>	<p>The learner realizes the rigors of crafting one's speech.</p>

<p>Instruction: Learners will be presenting an extemporaneous speech by answering the question/image that they will pick. Possible questions and images will be given beforehand, but the students will pick their questions on the day and time of the presentation. Each student will only be given 2 minutes to answer the question or explain the image.</p>	
--	--

The data in Table 8 presented several speaking and listening activities used in the Senior High School curriculum and their alignment with specific content standards. Activities such as “What’s with the Conversation,” “Speech Evaluation,” and “Mini Documentary” aimed to develop learners’ understanding of the elements, functions, and strategies of oral communication. These tasks reflected a performance-based and context-driven approach where students were encouraged to engage in real-life speech situations through dramatization, critical evaluation, and documentary production. Additionally, the inclusion of various speech deliveries—manuscript, memorized, and extemporaneous—demonstrated that the tasks are scaffolded to support different communication styles and learner competencies.

Based on recent literature, alignment between speaking and listening activities and content standards was vital in fostering communicative competence. According to Genon and Torres (2020), learners benefited most when classroom activities mirrored real-world communication demands, enhancing both engagement and learning outcomes. Similarly, a study by Fan-Wei Kung (2016) highlighted that the use of authentic language input and real-life communication contexts significantly improved learners’ oral communicative competence, as it provided meaningful opportunities for interaction and language use beyond isolated practice. These findings affirmed the pedagogical validity of the tasks in Table 8, which collectively addressed the multifaceted nature of oral communication ranging from content delivery and speech crafting to intercultural interaction thereby promoting holistic language development among students

Table 9
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Performance Standards in Grade 8

Activity	Performance Standards
<p>Activity 1: Informative Speech Instruction: Listen closely to a recorded speech provided by your teacher, then answer the following questions with a minimum of 3</p>	<p>The learner selects and uses listening strategies appropriate to the purpose and demonstrates comprehension by formulating relevant and insightful questions.</p>

<p>sentences and a maximum of 5 sentences.</p> <p>Activity 2: Listening Strategies Instruction: Listen to the audiobook from the link provided. Afterwards, come up and write 5 questions regarding the audio you have listened to. Write your questions below.</p>	
<p>Activity 3: Instruction: Watch closely and examine a TED Talk, and then in 3-5 sentences answer the questions that follow:</p>	<p>The learner demonstrates comprehension of multimedia texts by making personal and critical connections and evaluating the speaker’s delivery and persuasive techniques.</p>
<p>Activity 4: Instruction: For your activity, listen to the speech entitled “The Power of Listening” by William Ury. You need to apply the strategies in listening to the speech, then after that you will write your observations, especially the important information that you’ve heard in the speech. Write your answer on your answer sheet.</p>	<p>The learner identifies the speaker’s purpose, tone, and message and applies selective listening strategies to extract key ideas.</p>

Table 9 showcased listening and speaking tasks designed for Grade 8 students, with an emphasis on enhancing listening comprehension, question formulation, and critical evaluation of spoken texts. Activities such as listening to recorded speeches, audiobooks, and TED Talks were paired with tasks like writing questions, identifying key ideas, and analyzing tone and purpose. These activities directly corresponded to performance standards that prioritized appropriate use of listening strategies, critical interpretation of multimedia texts, and extraction of key information. Overall, the activities were structured to gradually build students’ analytical listening skills, supporting both basic understanding and higher-order thinking.

The integration of authentic materials such as TED Talks and well-known speeches reflected best practices in language instruction, promoting learner engagement and contextual relevance. As suggested by Richards (2019), using authentic texts enhanced learners’ exposure to natural language use and strengthened their pragmatic competence. Moreover, recent curriculum guidelines underscored the importance of fostering strategic listening to develop comprehension skills suited to various purposes and contexts. The tasks in Table 4 effectively aligned with these standards by blending comprehension checks with reflective responses, ensuring that students were not only decoding content but also interpreting meaning critically.

Table 10
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Performance Standards in Grade 10

Activity	Performance Standards
<p>Activity 1: Evaluating Spoken Text Instruction: Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below, then identify which among the three videos shows fluency, tone, cohesion, and correctness. Afterwards, answer the following questions below.</p>	<p>The learner composes a short but powerful persuasive text using a variety of persuasive techniques and devices.</p>
<p>Activity 2: Detecting Biases and Unsupported Claims Instruction: For your activity, you are going to watch and listen critically to a debate on the link given below. Since it's a debate, you are on the mediator side. You are to list at least 5 biases and the unsupported claims (if there are any) that the two opponents said. Note that you are not to repeat everything that the mediator has said. Follow the given format.</p> <p>Activity 3: Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below. Afterwards, in 3-4 sentences, answer the following questions in the space provided.</p>	<p>The learner proficiently delivers an argumentative speech emphasizing how to resolve conflicts among individuals.</p>
<p>Activity 4: Memorized Speech Instruction: For your application, you are going to deliver the speech that you just made. The delivery of speech should be memorized, note that you will be guided with the criteria below.</p>	<p>The learner skillfully delivers a speech for a special occasion through utilizing effective verbal and non-verbal strategies and ICT resources.</p>

The table presented a set of Grade 10 listening and speaking activities aligned with performance standards. These activities were designed to enhance learners' critical thinking, speech evaluation, argumentative skills, and delivery techniques. Each task focused on analyzing spoken texts, detecting biases, and practicing speech delivery with different formats such as persuasive and memorized speeches. The activities not only

assessed students' listening comprehension but also their ability to express ideas clearly, cohesively, and persuasively through spoken language. These tasks contributed to developing learners' fluency and critical analysis in both formal and informal communication contexts.

Asep Maulana et. al (2020) claimed that when speaking and listening instruction was in line with communicative and performance-based standards, learners' communicative competence was greatly improved because both productive and receptive skills were developed in an integrated way. According to their research, students' language competency and meaningful communication abilities improved when listening and speaking were taught effectively.

Activities such as evaluating spoken texts and identifying unsupported claims allowed students to apply higher-order thinking skills, which were essential for both academic learning and real-life communication. This alignment supported the objectives of the Department of Education K to 12 curriculums in producing functionally literate citizens who were effective communicators.

Table 11
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Performance Standards in Senior High

Activity	Performance Standards
<p>Activity 2: What's with the Conversation Instruction: Learners will be grouped and will present a 5-minute skit of a communication process among people with diverse cultural background (intercultural communication). You may present a communication breakdown, effective communication, or both.</p>	<p>The learner designs and performs effective controlled and uncontrolled oral communication activities based on context. The learner demonstrates effective use of communicative strategy in a variety of speech situations.</p>
<p>Activity 3: Speech Evaluation Instruction: Learners will watch and listen to a sample oral communication video provided by the teacher. Then, point out and evaluate the functions used by the speaker to deliver ideas and evaluate how it was executed by writing a 200-250-word essay.</p>	<p>The learner writes a 250-word essay of his/her objective observation and evaluation of the various speakers watched and listened to.</p>
<p>Activity 5: Mini Documentary Instruction: Create a 3-5-minute video that captures the seven communicative strategies in different</p>	<p>The learner demonstrates effective use of communicative strategy in a variety of speech situations.</p>

speech situations. Choose a place inside the campus (classroom, canteen, bookstore, library, chapel) where people are involved in some kind of an activity.

Activity 6: Reading from a Manuscript
 Instruction: Learners will be reading the manuscript that they have done.

Activity 7: Memorized Speech
 Instruction: Learners will be presenting a short speech that they have memorized.

Activity 8: Extemporaneous Speech
 Instruction: Learners will be presenting an extemporaneous speech by answering the question/image that they will pick. Possible questions and images will be given beforehand but the students will pick their questions on the day and time of presentation. Each student will only be given 2 minutes to answer the question or explain the image.

The learner proficiently delivers various speeches using the principles of effective speech delivery.

Table 11 showcased listening and speaking tasks for senior high school students, focusing on deeper and more contextual communication skills. These include intercultural communication, speech evaluation, mini-documentary production, and various forms of speech delivery. Each activity was performance-based, requiring learners to engage in realistic communication scenarios where they applied their understanding of communicative strategies. This progression highlighted the increasing complexity and integration of skills expected at the senior high school level, with a strong emphasis on context, delivery, and purpose.

Recent studies supported the use of authentic and context-based tasks in senior high school as effective strategies in developing oral communication proficiency. As noted by Salendab and Dapitan (2021), performance-based assessments, such as mini-documentaries and extemporaneous speeches, fostered real-world communication skills and critical reflection. These tasks reinforced learners' ability to adapt their speech to various situations, enhancing both their linguistic and pragmatic competence. This ensured that students were prepared for higher education, employment, and civic participation.

Table 12
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Learning Competencies in Grade 8

Activity	Learning Competencies
<p>Activity 1: Informative Speech Instruction: Listen closely to a recorded speech provided by your teacher then answer the following questions with a minimum of 3 sentences and a maximum of 5 sentences.</p> <p>Activity 2: Listening Strategies Instruction: Listen to the audio book from the link provided. Afterwards, come up and write 5 questions regarding to the audio you have listened. Write your questions below.</p>	<p>1.1 Use listening strategies based on purpose, topic familiarity, difficulty, and text type.</p> <p>1.2 Ask and answer questions about a listening material.</p>
<p>Activity 3 Instruction: Watch closely and examine a TEDTalk, and then in 3-5 sentences answer the questions that follow:</p>	<p>EN11/120C-Ia-7 - 2.1 Listen critically to different types of listening texts.</p> <p>2.2 Use information from multimedia sources to evaluate a speaker’s ideas.</p> <p>2.3 Make personal connections to ideas in a viewed or heard text.</p>
<p>Activity 4 Instruction: For your activity, listen to the speech entitled “The Power of Listening” by William Ury. You need to apply the strategies in listening the speech then after that you will write your observations, especially the important information that you’ve heard in the speech. Write your answer on your answer sheet.</p>	<p>3.1 Identify the speaker’s purpose and tone.</p> <p>EN11/120C-Ibe-14- 3.2 Evaluate the accuracy and truthfulness of ideas in a listening text.</p>

The table presented a series of listening and speaking activities for Grade 8 students that aligned with specific learning competencies. These tasks focused on developing students’ ability to use various listening strategies, comprehend spoken texts, and evaluate spoken content critically. The activities included listening to recorded speeches, analyzing multimedia sources like TED Talks, and applying listening strategies through reflection. These were carefully designed to promote not just passive listening

but active interpretation, questioning, and connection-making, which were essential for critical thinking and meaningful communication.

According to Cables (2025), integrating multimedia-based and reflective listening tasks significantly improved students' engagement and comprehension in English classes. The alignment shown in the table supports the development of higher-order thinking skills through active evaluation and analysis of speech content. Activities such as examining tone, identifying the speaker's purpose, and evaluating the truthfulness of statements directly contributed to strengthening learners' critical literacy, an essential 21st-century skill. Research by Mahardika (2025) showed that implementing critical literacy practices in English language teaching contexts promoted students' critical thinking, engagement, and analytical interpretation of texts, ultimately enhancing their communicative competencies in meaningful discourse.

Table 13
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Learning Competencies in Grade 10

Activity	Learning Competencies
<p>Activity 1: Evaluating Spoken Text Instruction: Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below then identify which among the three videos shows fluency, tone, cohesion, and correctness. Afterwards, answer the following questions below.</p>	<p>EN10LC-Ia-11.1: Get information that can be used in everyday life from news reports, speeches, informative talks, panel discussions, etc.</p> <p>EN10LC-Ib-4 -Determine the implicit and explicit signals, verbal, as well as non-verbal, used by the speaker to highlight significant points.</p>
<p>Activity 2: Detecting Biases and Unsupported Claims Instruction: For your activity, you are going to watch and listen critically in a debate on the link given below. Since it's a debate, you are on the mediator side. You are to list at least 5 biases and the unsupported claims (if there's any) that the two opponents said. Note that you are not to repeat everything that the mediator has said. Follow the given format.</p> <p>Activity 3</p>	<p>EN10LC-Ile-13.2- Employ analytical listening in problem solving.</p> <p>EN10LC-Ilg-13.3- Detect biases and prejudices.</p> <p>EN010LC-Ih-15.3- Determine unsupported generalizations and exaggerations.</p>

<p>Watch and listen critically to the video clips from the link given below. Afterwards, in 3-4 sentences, answer the following questions on the space provided.</p>	
<p>Activity 4: Memorized Speech Instruction: For your application, you are going to deliver the speech that you just made. The delivery of speech should be memorized, note that you will be guided with the criteria below.</p>	<p>EN100L-IIIh- 3.11- Produce the sounds of English correctly and effectively.</p> <p>EN100L-III d-1.4- Use polite expressions when giving a roast.</p> <p>EN100L-III e-3.9- Use the correct and appropriate language when giving a toast or a tribute to someone and when delivering welcome and closing remarks.</p>

The table illustrated the alignment of listening and speaking tasks with learning competencies in Grade 10. Each activity, such as evaluating spoken text, detecting biases, and delivering memorized speech, was designed to develop critical thinking, listening comprehension, and appropriate speech delivery. Activities were varied, including watching video clips, participating in debates, and delivering memorized speeches. These activities ensured that students not only analyzed spoken content but also applied what they learned through performance tasks, promoting a comprehensive approach to oral communication skills development.

According to recent curriculum frameworks, integrating interactive and performance-based tasks in language learning fostered communicative competence and critical thinking among learners Department of Education (2016). The use of real-life scenarios like debates and speech delivery aligned with the K to 12 curriculum's goal of preparing students for lifelong learning through relevant and meaningful tasks. Furthermore, these methods supported students in mastering both receptive and productive language skills, which were foundational to effective communication Richards (2019).

Table 14
Congruence of Listening and Speaking Tasks to Learning Competencies in Senior High School

Activity	Learning Competencies
<p>Activity 2: What's with the Conversation Instruction: Learners will be grouped and will present a 5-minute skit of a</p>	<p>EN11/120C-Ia-7- 2.1. Demonstrates sensitivity to the sociocultural dimension of communication situation.</p>

<p>communication process among people with diverse cultural background (intercultural communication). You may present a communication breakdown, effective communication, or both.</p>	
<p>Activity 3: Speech Evaluation Instruction: Learners will watch and listen to a sample oral communication video provided by the teacher. Then, point out and evaluate the functions used by the speaker to deliver ideas and evaluate how it was executed by writing a 200-250-word essay.</p>	<p>EN11/120C-Ia-7- 3.2. Evaluates the effectiveness of an oral communication activity.</p>
<p>Activity 5: Mini Documentary Instruction: Create a 3-5-minute video that captures the seven communicative strategies in different speech situations. Choose a place inside the campus (classroom, canteen, bookstore, library, chapel) where people are involved in some kind of an activity.</p>	<p>EN11/120C-Ifj-20- 4.1. Responds appropriately and effectively to a speech act.</p> <p>EN11/120C-IIab-21 - 5.1. Engages in a communicative situation using acceptable, polite and meaningful communicative strategies.</p>
<p>Activity 6: Reading from a Manuscript Instruction: Learners will be reading the manuscript that they have done.</p> <p>Activity 7: Memorized Speech Instruction: Learners will be presenting a short speech that they have memorized.</p> <p>Activity 8: Extemporaneous Speech Instruction: Learners will be presenting an extemporaneous speech by answering the question/image that they will pick. Possible questions and images will be given beforehand but the students will pick their questions on the day and time of presentation. Each student will only be given 2 minutes to answer the question or explain the image.</p>	<p>EN11/120C-Ifj-17- 6.1. Distinguishes types of speeches.</p> <p>EN11/120C-IIcj-25- 7.2. Uses principles of effective speech delivery</p>

This table presented listening and speaking activities in Senior High School, emphasizing higher-level competencies such as evaluating communication effectiveness, demonstrating intercultural sensitivity, and using appropriate speech strategies. Activities

like speech evaluation, mini-documentaries, and extemporaneous speaking highlighted a shift from basic listening skills to applied communication. These tasks were more complex and required students to analyze, perform, and reflect on communication in various contexts, thereby developing both cognitive and sociolinguistic competencies.

As learners progressed to senior high school, educational standards emphasized the need for deeper communication skills that considered cultural and situational appropriateness. Current pedagogical practices promoted task-based learning to equip students with real-world communication proficiency, fostering global readiness. A study by Nasir (2024) discovered that task-based language instruction greatly improved high school students' communicative competence to enhanced engagement, collaboration, and real-world communication outcomes. The inclusion of authentic tasks like extemporaneous and memorized speeches ensured that students were prepared to participate meaningfully in academic, professional, and social contexts Larsen-Freeman & Anderson (2016).

Output of the Study

The output titled “Bridging Listening and Speaking Competencies: Practical Assessment Tasks Aligned with Learning Standards” focuses on developing students' overall communicative competence through integrated listening and speaking activities. The study presented engaging assessment tasks that matched learners' cognitive and linguistic abilities across grade levels.

The results showed a structured integration of listening and speaking tasks aligned with learning standards and students' developmental needs. Listening activities such as “Rebuild the Message” (Grade 8) and “Podcast Deep Dive” (Grade 10) used both top-down and bottom-up strategies to improve comprehension by helping students identify main ideas, details, and reflections from auditory texts. The increasing complexity of tasks across grade levels also demonstrated the gradual development of listening skills. Meanwhile, speaking activities emphasized fluency, clarity, and confidence. Tasks like “Quick Talk” encouraged impromptu speaking, while “Show and Tell” in Senior High School developed students' ability to organize and present information clearly. These activities supported meaningful communication and were aligned with specific content and performance standards.

Overall, the study highlighted the importance of well-designed communicative tasks that integrated listening and speaking, helping students apply language skills effectively while building both competence and confidence.

Summary of Findings

From the results and discussion, the following findings were presented.

1. The results showed that top-down listening processes dominated the activities, with a strong focus on using prior knowledge, context, and inference to derive meaning. In

contrast, bottom-up listening skills such as decoding sounds, recognizing words, and processing grammar were minimally addressed. Additionally, the tasks primarily targeted listening for specific details or stated facts, while listening for gist was largely absent. All activities fell under focused listening, limiting exposure to a broader range of listening types and potentially hindering the development of comprehensive listening skills.

2. The results revealed that memorized speech was the most common mode of delivery at 50%, followed by extemporaneous speech at 33.33%, and manuscript speech at 16.67%. Impromptu speech was notably absent, indicating a strong focus on prepared rather than spontaneous speaking. In terms of speech types, informative speech was the most frequently practiced at 50%, followed by persuasive speech at 33.34%. Entertainment and demonstrative speeches were the least emphasized, each appearing only once, showing minimal focus on these more creative or specialized forms of speaking.

3. Grade 8 activities emphasized foundational skills like listening, questioning, and interpreting oral texts. Grade 10 focused on critical thinking through speech criticism, bias detection, and formal speech delivery, mainly persuasive and memorized speeches. Senior High School activities were performance-based and context-specific, involving intercultural communication, speech critiques, and mini-documentary production. Content and performance standards were well-aligned across levels. Top-down listening strategies dominated, with limited use of bottom-up approaches. Speaking tasks mainly involved prepared speech types, with minimal inclusion of spontaneous formats like impromptu and entertainment speeches. Integration of listening and speaking tasks was present, but task variety and engagement remained limited.

Conclusions

The findings led the researchers to the following conclusions. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrived at the following conclusions.

1. The listening assessment tasks showed a strong reliance on Top-Down processing, with little to no inclusions of Bottom-Up strategies that supported foundational listening skills. The focus on listening for specific details limited students' opportunities to develop broader comprehension through Listening for Gist. While the tasks required attentive and active engagement, a more balanced approach was needed to support both basic and higher-level listening skills.

2. The speaking assessment tasks and tools used in Junior and Senior High School activities emphasized prepared and structured speech delivery, with a strong focus on Memorized and Extemporaneous speeches. The absence of Impromptu Speech highlighted a lack of opportunities for spontaneous, real-time communication practice. Similarly, the dominance of Informative and Persuasive speeches suggested a focus on academic and practical communication skills, while the limited use of Entertainment and Demonstrative speeches indicated less attention to creative and specialized speaking styles. These findings pointed to the need for a more varied approach to speaking tasks

that could help students to develop a broader and more flexible range of speaking competencies.

3. In conclusion, the study emphasized the effective progression of listening and speaking tasks from Grades 8 through Senior High School, highlighting the alignment with curriculum standards and the development of key communication competencies. The tasks evolved from foundational skills in Grade 8 to more complex and performance-based activities in Senior High School, encouraging students to engage critically with spoken content and express themselves with purpose and structure. Although the alignment with educational benchmarks was generally strong, the findings suggested the importance of diversifying listening strategies and incorporating more spontaneous and creative speaking formats. This would not only enhance students' listening and speaking skills but also better prepare them for real-world communication scenarios. The study advocated for a continuous refinement of assessment tasks to foster both academic and practical communication competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations were made to enhance the alignment and effectiveness of speaking and listening assessment tasks and tools with the standards and competencies set for junior and senior high school students.

1. Educators were advised to design and implement tasks that directly reflected the learning competencies and real-world communication scenarios. They should also engage in continuous professional development to effectively evaluate and support students' speaking and listening skills.
2. Students were encouraged to take an active role in practicing authentic speaking and listening tasks to improve their communicative competence. They are also encouraged to seek feedback and use assessment results to guide their language learning progress.
3. Curriculum Developers were recommended to ensure that assessment tools and tasks are clearly aligned with national standards and learner outcomes. Additionally, they were encouraged to consider integrating communicative and contextualized activities that fostered both academic and practical language use.
4. Future researchers were suggested to replicate this study in diverse educational settings-such as private schools, rural and urban institutions, or alternative learning environments to examine whether similar patterns in speaking and listening assessment alignment existed. Replicating the study with larger or more varied participant groups could enhance the generalizability of the results and provide further evidence for improving language assessment practices across different contexts.

Acknowledgements

This research would not have been successfully completed without the invaluable support and assistance of several individuals who generously shared their time, knowledge, and expertise. The researchers would like to express their heartfelt appreciation to their research adviser and research instructor for their constant guidance, constructive feedback, and encouragement throughout the conduct of the study. They also extend their gratitude to the panel members, statistician, and research validators for their insightful comments, technical support, and recommendations that greatly contributed to the improvement of the research. The researchers are also deeply thankful to their parents for their continuous support, motivation, and understanding. Above all, they gave thanks to Almighty God for the wisdom, strength, and perseverance bestowed upon them in the successful completion of this study.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (2016). *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives: Complete Edition*. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/=1223916>
- Asep Maulana, A., Izzuddin Musthafa, I., & Titin Nur Hayati, T. N. (2020). *The Efficiency of Teaching Listening and Speaking Skills to Develop Students' Communicative Competences*. Retrieved from <http://www.hrpub.org/download/20200229/UJER10-19591159.pdf>
- Caballes, A. (2025). *Effectiveness of multimedia integration on the academic performance in Grade 10 English*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/395425937_Effectiveness_of_Multimedia_Integration_on_the_Academic_Performance_in_Grade_10_English
- Capadeso, R. A., & Banquiao, Q. M. (2025). *Factors Influencing Language Proficiency Among Grade 12 Learner*. Retrieved from <https://www.dinkumpublishers.com/djsi/d-0441/>
- Department of Education (2016). *K to 12 English Curriculum Guide*. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/English-CG.pdf>
- Fan-Wei Kung (2016). *Facilitating Learners' Second Language Communicative Competence through the Development of Media Literacy: A Conversation Analytic Approach*. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1180865>
- Field, J. (2019). *Second language listening: Where are we?* Retrieved from <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/Images/524275-second-language-listening-where-are-we-john-field-cambridge-english-teacher-.pdf>
- Genon, L. J. D., & Torres, C. B. (2020). *Constructive alignment of assessment practices in English language classrooms*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351078387_Constructive_alignment_of_assessment_practices_in_English_language_classrooms
- Goh, C. C. M., & Aryadoust, V. (2025). *Developing and assessing second language listening and speaking: Does AI make it better?* Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/394104512>
- Larsen-Freeman, D., & Anderson, M. (2016). *Techniques and principles in language teaching* (3rd ed.). Retrieved from https://openlibrary.org/books/OL24855325M/Techniques_and_principles_in_language_teaching

- Mahardika, A. A. (2025). Incorporating Critical Literacy in English Language Teaching (ELT). Retrieved from <https://journal.ubm.ac.id/index.php/english-language-culture/article/>
- Marquez, S. L., & Bandoy, M. M. (2020). K to 12 English Curriculum Guide Implementation and Performance in Public Secondary Schools Retrieved from <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/351835-k-to-12-english-curriculum-guide-impleme-7031a0bb.pdf>
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2016). Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.orgID=2631333>
- Miradora, S. S. (2022). Teachers' Evaluation of the K to 12 Junior High School English Curriculum and Its Implementation Retrieved from <https://www.ioer-imrj.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Teachers-Evaluation-of-the-K-12-Junior-High-School-English-Curriculum-and-Its-Implementation.pdf>
- Nasir, A. R. (2024). The Effectiveness of Task Based Language Teaching in Enhancing High School Students' Communicative Competence. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/397107201>
- Newton, J. M., & Nation, P. (2020). Teaching ESL/EFL listening and speaking. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343900589_Teaching_ESLEFL_Listening_and_Speaking
- Richards, J. C. (2019). Curriculum Development in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352543528_Curriculum_Development_in_Language_Teaching
- Salendab, F. A., & Dapitan, Y. C. (2021). Effectiveness of performance-based assessment tools (PBATs) and the students' academic performance. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360539052_Effectiveness_of_Performance-Based_Assessment_Tools_PBATs_and_the_Students'_Academic_Performance
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2017). Differentiated instruction. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3687438>
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2014). The Differentiated Classroom: Responding to the Needs of All Learners (2nd Ed.). Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3209348>
- Wilson, J. J. (2018). Micro listening skills. In J. I. Lontas (Ed.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching* (pp. 1–6). John Wiley & Sons. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373241291_Micro_Listening_Skills